

Factors Deriving Consumers' Repurchase Intention in Online Shopping: a Pakistani Consumer's Perspective

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Abstract:

This research paper is intended to determine the most critical factors in the success of online businesses. The purpose of this research is to find out the most important antecedents of online repurchase intentions in Pakistani environment. For this purpose 180 respondents were chosen on the basis of convenient sampling. Regression coefficients were estimated by using SPSS 20 program. Some useful insights were found by the results. It is established that perceived ease of use, perceived enjoyment and satisfaction with the seller are the critical success factors that force any consumer to repurchase from the same online seller. Also this study has a few limitations. A future research with larger sample size and additional variables is recommended.

Keywords: Online repurchase intent, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, Trust, perceived enjoyment, Satisfaction with seller

1. INTRODUCTION:

The advent of internet has revolutionized the way business was conducted in the past. With the advancements in internet and e-commerce, consumers' preferences have been changed from conventional physical stores to online shopping. Online shopping refers to purchasing goods and (or) services by the use of internet. Online shopping offers great benefits at low cost to the consumers; the whole process of purchasing goods or services becomes convenient e.g. ease with which information can be assessed, plenty of alternate products, suitable alternate evaluation and product comparisons, 24/7 accessibility and time saving (Wen et al., 2011). There is no limitation as to time and place; customers can have easy and quick access to every product or service simply by some clicks (Adnan, 2014).

The massive use of internet and e-commerce not only resulted in ease for consumers but also opened large business opportunities for the marketers (Guan and Cheng, 2009). It not only forced sellers to offer their products and services online but also there is a great opportunity for them to gain competitive edge. They can get to those customers who prefer to buy online instead of visiting the physical outlet or store. This means reaching to that profitable segment of the society which is not being targeted by every other seller.

Javadi et al. (2012) argue that despite all the advantages there are a few drawbacks for the consumers for which they are reluctant to purchase online e.g. unable to being having a sense of product quality over the website, there is a risk due to lack of trust and no face to face communication. However this can be overcome by using online product recommendation agents (Xiao and Benbasat, 2007).

Online retailers and internet marketers need to understand shoppers' behavior and purchase preference while shopping online. It has been argued that determinants of online purchasing and repurchasing should be known to online retailers in order to have a clear idea about the important points to be kept in mind while promoting and designing online offers. Many researchers have previously studied and examined various factors that influence online shoppers behavior however there is still room for improvement. There is a need to conduct an empirical study in a developing country like Pakistan where there is a lot of potential but slow growth of e-commerce compared to developed nations. Although the internet adoption rate is slow but it is growing continuously and is expected to rise in near future (Adnan, 2014).

This research is intended to investigate and answer the following research questions:

1. How does perceived ease of use impacts online repurchase intent?

2. How does perceived usefulness results in online repeat purchasing?
3. What is the role of trust in online repurchase intent?
4. Does perceived enjoyment in online shopping have a role in online repurchase intent?
5. What is the role of satisfaction with the seller in online repurchase intent?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

2.1. Repurchase Intent

In marketing many researchers have highlighted the importance of repeat purchasing. All sellers are interested in knowing how consumers make their purchase decisions and what motivates them to repurchase. Repeat purchasing is the main source of revenues and long-term relationship building for retail businesses (Gupta & Kim, 2007). This not only brings revenues for the firm but also depicts positive association from the consumer side which later could result in positive word of mouth and loyal customers for the firm. But maintaining online customers is more tricky and challenging for sellers because of lack of face to face interaction. And it becomes difficult to assess the trustworthiness of the seller (Pavlou, Liang, & Xue, 2007).

Repurchasing has been defined by Chou and Hsu (2016) as “a customer’s re-use of the online channel to buy from a specific retailer”. It has been confirmed many times that repeat customers brings more profits to the firm as experienced customers are less costly to maintain and as they already are familiar with the online purchasing process, they spend less time in evaluating and making a purchase (Chiu et al., 2014).

The theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) (Ajzen and Fishbein, 1980) has been applied to enlighten human behavior. It states that the main precedent of human behavior is intention which is formed by perceived subjective norms. This theory can be used to predict consumer behavior as consumer behavior is dependent on what they think and perceive (Javadi et al., 2012). Many researches in past have focused on knowing the motivators behind repeat purchasing for sustaining online success (Chou and Hsu, 2016; Hsu et al., 2015; Chen et al., 2016) which is especially critical to be successful in this era of stiff competition in online businesses. Most of the researches conducted previously were focused on a specific online stores and services e.g. online auction, online bookstores, online banking, mobile internet and general online shopping stores etc (Chiu et al., 2012; Gupta and Kim, 2007; Bhattacharjee, 2001; Hong et al., 2006; and Qureshi et al., 2009). These researches were more focused on product or service related variables. However this research is based on finding the consumers’ perspective about generally all the items sold online whether products or services. For this purpose following variables are selected to generally test as determinant of repurchase intention: perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, trust, perceived enjoyment and satisfaction with the seller.

2.2. Perceived ease of use

Technology acceptance model (TAM) theory (proposed by Davis, 1989) suggests that there are two main variables that effect the users’ decision to use and adopt a new technology. These are: perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. These two are the basic factors in online repurchase intent too. Perceived ease of use has been defined as the degree to which a consumer sees the ease of connecting with a web based business and can get the item that he or she is looking for (Wen et al., 2011). It is considered to be one of the powerful element in describing repurchase behavior of a consumer. Rezaei and Amin(2013) have examined and established a significant relationship between perceived ease of use and repurchase intent. They concluded that simplicity in making an online purchase is going to result in repeating the purchase. Therefore it is hypothesized that:

H1: Perceived ease of use has a direct positive effect on online repurchase intent.

2.2. Perceived usefulness

Perceived usefulness has been described as the degree to which a consumer perceives that using web based business is going to be more productive (Rezaei and Amin, 2013). Previous researches have concluded that ease of use in a technology will increase consumers' perception of usefulness; which means that when consumers think it is simple to complete a transaction online, they will consider online shopping more useful (Wen et al., 2011). Al-Maghrabi et al., 2011 stated that if consumers' think it useful, they are going to repeat purchasing online even if they were not satisfied earlier. Perceived usefulness is going to result in repeat purchasing online. Usability is another important factor for achieving desired behavior.

H2: Perceived usefulness has a direct positive effect on online repurchase intent.

2.3. Trust

Trust means confidence which one person has that the other will behave as first person expects and the other would not take advantage of the situation at hand (Gefen et al., 2003). The role of trust is more important in online transactions as compared to conventional business transactions. Here trust refers to the consumer's belief that seller will meet his expectation and this trust motivates him/her to accept and complete an online transaction. Previous researches suggest that trust is an important factor that facilitates the online transaction by alleviating the effect of uncertainty (Hsu et al., 2015). Majority of the researchers in past have focused their attention on trust as a factor for achieving initial consumer acceptance in online purchase and very few have seen it as an important factor for continuing using the same website (Wang and Chiang, 2009). Trust has been accepted as an important facilitator that supports online purchasing and repurchasing (Chiu et al., 2009; Badrinarayanan et al., 2010; Rezaei and Amin, 2013). Trust has been established a major predictor of repeat purchasing.

H3: Trust has a direct positive effect on online repurchase intent.

2.4. Perceived enjoyment

Enjoyment is defined as "an awareness of holistic sensation when people are totally involved in a certain activity" (Csikszentmihalyi, 1975). The element of enjoyment in online shopping is as much important as it is in conventional physical store shopping. Entertaining, enjoyable and interesting online shopping experience has critical impact on consumer behavior (Koufaris, 2002). In online shopping enjoyment depends on the number of factors like the design of website, arrangement of products, ease with which comparisons can be done, available information and visuals etc. overall enjoyable experience is going to result in customer satisfaction that will affect future repurchase decision. It has been established in previous researches that customer's high enjoyment at e-commerce website positively affects customer's repurchase intention. Therefore

H4: Customers' perceived enjoyment has a positive effect on online repurchase intent.

2.5. Satisfaction with the seller

One of the most crucial factors for continued relation in any transaction is satisfaction. E-satisfaction has been defined by Flavián et al (2006) as "an affective consumer condition towards the web site that results from an evaluation of all the aspects that make up the consumer relationship". Satisfaction has been established as one of the major antecedent of loyalty (Finn et al., 2009). The relationship between satisfaction and loyalty has been proven by many recent studies e.g. Lin and Lekhawipat (2014) concluded that in comparison to unsatisfied customers, satisfied customers are expected to purchase again. Loyal customers are more profitable for companies as well. The relationship between satisfaction and online repurchase intention has been established by many recent previous studies e.g. Bulut, 2015; Rezaei and Amin, 2013; Chou and Hsu, 2016 etc. Therefore, it is hypothesized that

H5: Satisfaction with the seller has a positive effect on online repurchase intent.

Figure 1: Hypothesized model

3. METHODOLOGY:

The purpose of this research is to test the impact of determinants of online repurchase intent. For this purpose 180 respondents were selected out of the population. Convenience sampling was used to collect data from those individuals who had online shopping experience. Data was collected by using a structured questionnaire. The instrument was based on five point likert scale (strongly disagree=1, disagree 2, neither agree nor disagree=3, agree=4 and strongly agree=5). The items were selected from different researches (Table 1). SPSS 20 was used for data analysis.

Table 1: Selection of measurement items

Variables and items	Selected from
<p><i>Perceived ease of use</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The online shopping website is easy to use 2. The online shopping website is flexible to interact with 3. It is easier to use the Internet to find products that I want to buy 	Davis (1989), Gefen et al. (2003) & Enrique et al. (2008)
<p><i>Perceived usefulness</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Using the Internet enables me to finish my shopping tasks more quickly 2. Using the Internet for shopping helps me to make better purchase decisions 3. Using the Internet makes it easier to make purchases 4. Using the Internet for shopping saves me money 5. Overall, I find using the Internet for shopping useful 	Davis(1989) & Enrique et al. (2008)
<p><i>Trust</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I feel safe in my transactions with the website/online store 2. I believe the website can protect my privacy 3. I select online stores, which I believe are honest 4. I feel that this online vendor would provide me with good service 5. I feel that the online vendor is trustworthy 	Gefen et al. (2003), & Hassanein and Head (2007)
<p><i>Perceived enjoyment</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I found my visit to this website interesting 2. I found my visit to this website entertaining 3. I found my visit to this website enjoyable 4. I found my visit to this website pleasant 	Van der Heijden et al. (2003) & Hassanein and Head (2007)
<p><i>Satisfaction with the seller</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I feel good regarding my decision to purchase products from this seller 2. I think that purchasing products online from this seller is a good idea 3. I am satisfied with the overall online purchase experience with the seller 	Kim et al. (2004), Teo et al. (2009), Wang and Liao (2008)
<p><i>Online Repurchase intent</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If I could, I would like to continue purchasing products online as much as possible 2. I plan to continue using online shopping in the future rather than using traditional shopping 3. It is likely that I will continue purchasing products from the online stores in the future 	Chiu et al. (2012) (Modified for online shopping)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Table 2: Demographics characteristics (N=180)

Demographic Attributes		Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	74	41.1%
	Female	106	58.9%
Total		180	100
Age	Below 35 years	95	52.8%
	35-50 years	77	42.8%
	Above 50 years	8	4.4%
Total		180	100
Experience of online purchasing	Less than 3 months	18	10%
	3-6 months	45	25%
	6-12 months	44	24.4%
	1-3 years	40	22.2%
	3-5 years	25	13.9%
	More than 5 years	8	4.4%
Total		180	100

The final sample consisted of 180 respondents out of which 41.1 percent were male and 58.9 percent were female. If we look at the age statistics, 52.8% of the respondents are below 35 years of age, 42.8% are between 35 years and 50 years and 4.4% are above 50 years of age. It means majority of the respondents are young males and females which depicts that majority of online consumers are young. Next if we look at the experience of our respondents in online purchasing, statistics show that 25% have 3 to 6 months purchasing experience; 24.4% have 6 to 12 months experience; 22.2% of respondents have been involved in online shopping from 1 to 3 years; 13.9% have 3 to 5 years of online purchasing experience; 10% have less than 3 months experience and 4.4% have more than 5 years of online purchasing experience.

Figure 2: Type of product/service purchased online

Figure 2 is showing the type of product or service which has been purchased by the respondents. 33 percent of the products purchased online are related to apparel and accessories category while 19 percent books and

magazines were purchased by the respondents. Of all the products or services purchased by the respondents, 17 percent consisted of cinema tickets and 16 percent electronic goods and gadgets, 9 percent financial services and 6 percent other goods/services were purchased.

Figure 3: Amount spent on online shopping

Total amount spent by the respondents in online shopping is depicted through pie diagram (Figure 3). 58 percent of the respondents spent up to Rs. 5, 000 in online shopping. It means majority of the selected sample spent lesser amount in online transactions. About 25 percent of the respondents spent more than Rs. 5, 000 and up to Rs. 10, 000; 12 percent people spent more than Rs. 10,000 and less than Rs. 15,000. Only 4 percent respondents spent more than Rs.15, 000 while there are only 1 percent of all respondents who spent more than Rs. 20, 000.

Table 3: Alpha Reliability Coefficients

Measures	No. of items	Alpha Coefficients
Perceived ease of use	3	0.759
Perceived usefulness	5	0.726
Trust	5	0.776
Perceived enjoyment	4	0.792
Satisfaction with the seller	3	0.838
Online Repurchase intent	3	0.815

Table 3 explains the number of items used against each variable and the alpha reliability coefficients. All the coefficients are above 0.7 which is showing the reliability of the instrument adapted for the purpose. The maximum value of the alpha coefficient is 0.838 which is related to satisfaction with the seller and minimum is 0.726 which is connected with perceived usefulness.

Table 4: Hypotheses Summary

Causal Paths			Hypotheses	Regression Coefficients	CR (t-value)	p-value	Results
ORPI	<---	PEOU	H1	0.310	4.621	***	Accepted
ORPI	<---	PU	H2	-0.016	-0.202	ns	Rejected
ORPI	<---	TR	H3	0.105	1.255	ns	Rejected
ORPI	<---	PE	H4	0.258	3.385	**	Accepted
ORPI	<---	SAT	H5	0.305	5.129	***	Accepted

(ORPI= Online Repurchase Intention, PEOU=Perceived Ease of Use, PU= Perceived Usefulness, TR=Trust, PE=Perceived Enjoyment, SAT=Satisfaction with the seller)

*** p<0.001, ** p=0.001, ns= not significant

This study aimed at identifying the important determinants of online repurchase intention and how these factors influence the repurchase behavior in Pakistan. 3 out of all 5 hypotheses were supported and 2 were not found to be significant. The support of hypothesis 1, 4 and 5 depicts that perceived ease of use, perceived enjoyment and satisfaction with the seller are more important predictor of online repurchase intent. Table 4 enlists all the regression coefficients, t-value, p-value and the decision regarding acceptance or rejection of the hypotheses. For this purpose regression coefficients were estimated using SPSS 20 program. First of all in order to check the impact of perceived ease of use on online repurchase intention, the regression coefficient was estimated and it is having a positive value of 0.310 and also ($p < 0.05$) which means perceived ease of use is having a positive effect on online repurchase intention. It is showing that 1 percent increase in perceived ease of use will bring 31 percent increase in online repurchase intentions. This result is also consistent with the results of Wen et al. (2011),

In order to test the second hypothesis, regression coefficient of perceived usefulness on online repurchase intention was estimated and it was found that the beta value was not significant ($p > 0.05$) and also beta value was -0.016. This shows that the second hypothesis is not only being rejected but also perceived usefulness is having negative relation with online repurchase intent. Although in many previous studies it was found positive and significant but in the current study, results are just opposite. Another study matching the same results could not be found to the best of author's efforts. Similarly third hypothesis was also rejected on account of not being significant ($p > 0.05$). Although the relationship between trust and online repurchase intent was established by Hsu et al. (2015), wanida (2015) and Razak et al. (2014).

Fourth and fifth hypotheses were tested and regression coefficients were estimated. From the results, it is clear that perceived enjoyment and satisfaction with the seller is having positive effect on online repurchase intention (also $p < 0.05$). The beta values are 0.258 and 0.305 respectively; which means that one percent increase in perceived enjoyment will bring 25.8 percent increase in online repurchase intention and one percent increase in satisfaction will increase online repurchase intention by 30.5 percent. Both hypotheses are accepted. These results are also significant with previous studies. The relationship between perceived enjoyment and online repurchase intent was also confirmed by Wen et al. (2011). Similarly impact of satisfaction and online repurchase intention was established by many previous studies e.g. Rezaei and Amin, (2013), Hsu et al. (2015), Hsu et al. (2014)

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was conducted to determine the crucial factors for the success of online businesses. The impact of five major variables was studied in order to confirm the most significant factors. The results of the study provide some useful insights. According to the results, the most important factors which motivate any consumer to repurchase again and again are perceived ease of use of the website, customers' perception regarding the

enjoyable experience and their satisfaction with the seller. The other two variables (trust and perceived usefulness) are also important but were not found significant for the sample under study. This study had some limitations e.g. sample was selected on the basis of convenient sampling. Also the sample size was not very large. The same study replicated elsewhere and with a larger sample may produce different results because demographic diversity may provide dissimilar results. Future studies may be conducted by taking additional variables as well e.g. role of reputation of the seller, perceived value and loyalty etc.

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